

Automated container vessel docking: From Anchorage to Dock

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Abstract— Maritime transport remains the backbone of global trade, handling approximately 80% of total trade volume. As technological advancements continue to reshape logistics and supply chain operations, automation has emerged as a transformative force in the maritime sector. This paper explores the feasibility and implications of full automation in maritime freight transport, with a specific focus on automated berthing and unberthing of vessels. Drawing insights from the EU-funded AutoMoTIF project, it examines the benefits, challenges, and technological gaps associated with automation in port operations. Through an in-depth analysis of a use case, the paper identifies key operational, safety, environmental, and cybersecurity considerations, highlighting the role of digital twins as a critical enabler for seamless integration. The findings contribute to the ongoing discussion on maritime automation, highlighting the necessity of overcoming interoperability issues, regulatory hurdles, and workforce adaptation challenges to achieve a fully autonomous maritime transport system.

Keywords— maritime freight transport, automation, berthing of freight vessels, port terminal, open reference architecture

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the latest (2024) United Nations Review of maritime report, 80% of global trade volume is transported by sea, reaching 12,292 million tons in 2023 [1]. In the EU, maritime transport is responsible for almost 68% of freight transport performance (in ton-km based on 2022 data), followed by road transport with 25%. A coastline is a feature that 22 of all EU members have; for 15 of those countries, maritime is the main mode of freight transport, accounting for more than 70% in 10 of them [2].

In recent decades, automation has brought radical changes in many different fields, including freight transportation, creating opportunities but at the same time introducing new challenges [3], as well as uncertainty [4]. The increasing demand for faster, more efficient, and accurate deliveries has driven the adoption of advanced technologies at all stages of the supply chain [5]. As an indispensable component of freight transport, the maritime industry is also being transformed with the growing use of technological innovations and digitalization, aiming at enhancing safety, efficiency and sustainability [6].

In this direction, the objective of this paper is to identify the benefits as well as the challenges posed by the use of automation in maritime freight transport and logistics. The paper is based on the on-going research conducted in the context of the EU-funded AutoMoTIF¹ project. In this project, four use cases are employed to extract relevant user needs and understand technological gaps which will lead to developing technical specifications, different scenarios and concepts of operations. The use cases refer to different parts of the freight transport and logistics chain, namely; automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels, automated port operations, automated shunting as a service oriented platform and automated multimodal terminal operations. The results of all use cases will then be used to validate a new proposed open reference architecture framework for digital twins, one of the most prominent emerging technologies in the field.

This paper focuses on one of the use cases, the automated berthing/unberthing as part of the port call process. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows; initially, a literature review on automation in maritime freight transport is presented, focusing on benefits, challenges and barriers. The use case follows, and the paper concludes with some insights on how the proposed reference architecture enhanced with the use case's results can be used to move towards seamless automation in maritime freight transport and logistics.

II. AUTOMATION IN MARITIME FREIGHT TRANSPORT

Although there are currently several uses of automation in different aspects of maritime freight transport, especially in the areas of navigational aid, cargo handling and vessel management, most real-life applications are rather scattered, and there is still a long way to go until achieving the full integration of seamless automation in a common operational framework [6]. Emerging technologies play a crucial role in the introduction and implementation of automated processes, and it is through them that automation is being materialized and gaining potential. Several emerging technologies are being used in different applications in the field of freight maritime transport and logistics, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), big data analytics, blockchain technology and the aforementioned Digital Twins technology [7].

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The introduction of automation, while associated with numerous benefits, can also raise some social, cost, environmental and safety aspects that should not be disregarded. From a social perspective, the acceptance of change and the associated mind shift that is required to do so has proven to be one of the key challenges [8]. Embracing automation can mean that work positions are lost, and staff is displaced. While employers search for new ways to incorporate automation technologies in day-to-day activities, employees often develop an increasing fear that their role and specialization will no longer be necessary [9]. Individual perceptions regarding automation can be substantially affected by professional experience [10], with the replacement stress being more present in staff of older age and of more profound skillset, comparing to younger colleagues with limited work experience [11]. Nevertheless, a study conducted by the International Transport Forum [12], showed that higher-skilled and more educated workers have lower probabilities in becoming unemployed due to automation. Cultural elements, such as paradigm shifts and international trends, can have an impact on the governance of transport automation [13]. According to Mitraka [14], in port environments, the concepts of automation, safety and social sustainability are interconnected, and therefore the involvement of employees during the transition of operations to automation is essential. This is in line with the results of Gong et al. [15], who highlighted that the associated institutional and societal changes, and not automation per se, have a central role in formulating the employees' viewpoints.

The potential cost savings and future return on investment are major factors that influence the actions of decision-makers towards the adoption of automation, together with increasing resilience and transparency of supply chains [16]. Lee et al. [17] studied the cost-effectiveness of the introduction of fully autonomous trucks on the total operational costs and concluded that significant savings on operational costs could be achieved overall, although a new cost factor related to remote operation was identified. Tjaden and Flämig [18] on the other hand, focusing on urban logistics, claim that cost saving should be approached with caution, as e.g. having vehicles that are not driven by humans do not always lead to decrease in expenses, unless this is accompanied by technology costs' reduction.

Incompatibility between existing systems and the newly integrated automated ones can also often hinder the process of adapting to automation and introduce additional costs. Although the CO₂ footprint and the general environmental impact of operations can substantially decrease when automation is used due for instance to time savings, the increased energy requirements for the essential computing processes, such as training models with numerous parameters that come with it should not be neglected [9], [19]. Especially training large-scale AI deep learning models, requires an enormous volume of data, the processing of which takes place in energy intensive data centers. A recent study by MIT [20], estimates that, in case autonomous vehicles are widely adopted worldwide, the energy needed to run their computers could emit as much CO₂ as all the data centers that currently exist globally. Moreover, what is known as the Jevons paradox can occur; increased efficiency due to automation can lead to increased use, and therefore to rising overall energy consumption instead of limiting it [21], [22].

Enhancing safety is a primary drive for adopting automation in the transport and logistics sector, as automated processes are expected to reduce human error - a leading cause of accidents. However, automated systems are subject to potential cyberattacks under malevolent intentions. This risk becomes even more present moving towards the so-called Industry 5.0 era, characterized by a high level of automation and the integration of cyber - physical systems. As information technology is continuously merged with operation technology, cyber-attacks can easily threaten critical physical infrastructure, with consequences that can range from supply chain disruptions, equipment damage and/or risk of workforce injuries to wider effects to public safety and the economy [23].

III. USE CASE: AUTOMATED BERTHING/UNBERTHING OF FREIGHT VESSELS

A. Definition, Scope and Objectives

In the realm of the automation of freight transportation, vessel port calls hold particular significance as they represent the critical junctures where maritime vessels interface with land-based logistics networks. These calls serve as orchestrated events that facilitate the seamless movement of goods across international borders and supply chains. Current research on vessel automation is primarily focused on enhancing vessel autonomy through the development of sophisticated navigation and control systems, addressing communication and connectivity challenges, improving situational awareness for collision avoidance and safety, and exploring commercial viability and necessary regulatory frameworks. However, there are significant gaps related to the automated operation of vessels when calling ports. Research that investigates parts of this process has been conducted in the context of EU-funded projects such as MOSES, AEGIS, AUTOSHIP and SEAMLESS focusing mainly on autonomous ship navigation, automated loading and unloading, automated manoeuvring and docking and shore control stations that deal with the exchange of data required for the technical integration rather than the business one.

One of the use cases that will take place in the context of the AutoMoTIF project focuses on investigating the potential advantages of utilizing automation across all phases of the port call process in terms of operational efficiency, safety, and environmental impact. This includes the vessel's arrival at the port, which encompasses the initial announcement, allocation of berth windows as well as the tugboats assignment. The process continues with the vessel's manoeuvring and docking, both performed by the assigned tugboats, followed by the stevedoring operations that secure the vessel on the quay to initiate the cargo loading and unloading processes. The undocking and manoeuvring of the vessel as it departs from the port is also included in the Use Case (UC).

The overall aim of the UC is to identify the basic requirements for a seamless automated port call process. To achieve this objective, it will simulate the entire process of berthing and unberthing at a generic port (i.e. container terminal), to replicate the complex interactions among the process key players with the assumption that the operation will be performed by fully autonomous tugboats (i.e., without a master onboard) and that an Automated Mooring System

(AMS) is installed at the quay. The simulation will incorporate various key parameters for the process, such as weather conditions, size of the vessel, number of tugboats, significant wave etc.

B. Actors, User Requirements and Technological Gaps

The actors involved in this UC (system actors or natural persons) are: Ship Agent, Pilot and/or Vessel Master, Vessel Traffic Services (VTS) Operator, Tugboat crew, Vessel crew, Berth Allocation System (BAS), Automated Mooring System (AMS), Autonomous tugboats and Shore Control Centre (SCC) Operator. The following user requirements have been identified in AutoMoTIF for the manoeuvring and mooring process, divided into operational and management requirements.

Operational:

- **Delay minimization:** The manoeuvring and mooring process is often delayed due to human factors e.g. miscommunication between tugboats and vessel pilots. The need for coordination is decreased significantly with autonomous tugboats, and therefore service can become faster and more efficient.
- **Safety enhancement:** The reduced involvement of humans in the operation of autonomous tugboats results in less people being exposed to risk during the manoeuvring process and also in limiting human errors due to fatigue and/or stress. Furthermore, eliminating the need for mooring ropes removes the associated hazards and risks.
- **Minimization of port emissions and air pollution:** When assisted by tugboats, vessels do not use their own propulsion means, and therefore the main contributor to emissions during the manoeuvring process are tugboat movements. Autonomous tugboats are expected to be more efficient in terms of the time required to berth the vessel and thus have less emissions (assuming the same type of engine used).

Management:

- **Real-time process monitoring:** Data exchanges between towed vessel, tugboats, and the port related to the progress of the operation, incl. the positions and speeds of the tugboats and the towed vessel, status of the mooring arrangements. The operation of autonomous tugboats combined with automated mooring systems will require acquiring the information related to the progress of the process, for ensuring real-time monitoring.
- **Provision of 24/7 port services:** Personnel working hours and resource limitations (e.g. tugboats, mooring equipment, etc.) due to increased port traffic, results in the tugboat assistance and mooring port services not being offered continuously, in contrast with autonomous tugboats and mooring systems, resulting in increasing the amount of traffic the port can handle any time during the day or night.

In order to integrate the autonomous tugboats within the port call process, there are some technological gaps that need to be addressed, mainly due to the inherent operational

complexity and the need to communicate effectively with all actors involved. These are the following:

- **Interaction of autonomous tugboats with conventional vessels:** The autonomous tugboats will operate in a confined area with other conventional vessels and therefore need to react to their movements, as well as exchange operational information when needed. In case autonomous tugboats do not react to the movement of other vessels in the area, there is a risk of collision. In case autonomous tugboats do not exchange information, other vessels will not be aware of their intentions.
- **Data exchange rate and management for real-time process monitoring:** The operation of the autonomous tugboats needs to be continuously monitored, which involves transmitting a large amount of information to the shore through a stable connection, which also needs to be managed on shore with respect to storage and maintaining adequate situational awareness for the monitoring agent. Transmitting all necessary data may lead to overloading the wireless connection. Furthermore, if the monitoring agent does not have an adequate understanding of the progress of the operation, the ability to intervene in case of failures will be limited.
- **Cybersecurity issues:** Vulnerabilities related to the need for the systems involved (i.e. autonomous tugboats, shore control, automated mooring system) to be wirelessly connected (e.g. to share information, to transfer control to the remote operator, etc.). Vulnerabilities may be exploited by external actors, e.g. to take over control of the autonomous tugboats, or disrupt their operation.

C. Technologies to Ensure Cybersecurity

As mentioned above, with the introduction of autonomous tugboats and the Automated Mooring System (AMS), the potential threats and vulnerabilities increase, as all systems become digitalized and rely on wireless connections for data exchange. These threats can be categorized into two main areas: the autonomous tugboats and the AMS. For the autonomous tugboats, the emerging threats include spoofing attacks on key system components such as GPS, LiDAR, and AIS. Additionally, communication between the autonomous tugboats and the Shore Control Center (SCC) is vulnerable to breaches. Regarding the AMS, spoofing is also a significant threat, along with potential ransomware attacks.

Currently, cybersecurity measures such as encrypted communication protocols between vessels and ports, firewalls on autonomous systems, and Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) assist in reducing various vulnerabilities and mitigate such threats. The same measures can be applied to autonomous tugboats and the AMS. Furthermore, utilizing a local 5G network within the terminal premises can enhance cybersecurity. Various additional fail-safe mechanisms can be implemented to further enhance autonomous tugboats operations, such as immobilization in case of a cyber-attack detection. Finally, the role of human acts as the last resort (barrier) in the event of an attack where the SCC operator may take control of the tugboats remotely or crew may control the tugboat manually on-board.

IV. THE AUTOMOTIF OPEN REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE FRAMEWORK FOR DIGITAL TWINS

In the current era, characterized by the demand for interoperability, modularity, and scalability, organizations face critical challenges when building and managing Digital Twins (DTs) [24] such as integration of diverse systems, scalability to meet expanding needs, customization for domain-specific requirements and ensuring security and data governance. To address these challenges, a new open digital twin reference architecture framework is developed in the context of the AutoMoTIF project. The framework provides a structured and modular approach to designing DTs that meet the demands of interoperability and scalability while also offering a foundation for future advancements. By focusing on three key layers; external integration, core functionality, and intermediary integration mechanisms, this architecture ensures a seamless flow of data and operations between external systems and the DTs' internal components [25].

The Open Architecture Framework serves as a critical enabler for the AutoMoTIF use cases, through guiding the implementation of essential functionalities in port automation, logistics optimization, and real-time visualization. By supporting seamless integration with IoT devices, AI models, simulation engines, and legacy systems, the architecture provides the tools needed to achieve greater levels of automation and decision-making efficiency. Through its scalability, the AutoMoTIF Open Reference Architecture ensures that all use cases can progressively activate and expand functionalities as they move towards higher levels of DT maturity. It lays the foundation for transforming port operations, streamlining logistics networks, and enhancing supply chain visibility, aligning each use case with the maturity progression and interoperability focus of each of the DT levels.

V. CONCLUSIONS

While bringing the promise of increased efficiency and sustainability, automation also comes with complexities - technical hurdles, cybersecurity risks, and the need for strong collaboration among stakeholders. The use case on automated berthing and unberthing illustrates both the potential and the obstacles associated with integrating autonomous systems in port operations. While digital twins and emerging technologies offer promising solutions, achieving full automation will require coordinated efforts among industry stakeholders, policymakers, and technology developers. Moving forward, a balanced approach - one that combines technological innovation with regulatory frameworks and workforce adaptation - will be essential to realizing the vision of an autonomous and resilient maritime transport ecosystem.

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